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THE CONCEPT OF CRITICAL THINKING TECHNOLOGY IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE LEARNING

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ABSTRACT

Critical thinking is the ability to pose questions, develop a variety of arguments, and make independent, thoughtful decisions. Therefore, the main idea of using technology for me is to create such an atmosphere of learning through game techniques, in which students, together with the teacher, actively communicate, consciously reflect on the learning process, monitor, confirm, refute or expand knowledge, new ideas, feelings or opinions about the world around them. And, of course, they do it quite fluently in English. In this article, I tried to systematize my experience on the use of critical thinking techniques in modern English lessons.

Keywords: critical thinking, creative active personality, interaction, challenge, cluster, motivation, understanding, information, development, reflection.

A teacher occupies a special place in a student's life and serves as the backbone of the school, shaping a sustainable future. Today's demands require a teacher to master modern knowledge and technology, possess high qualifications, and have deep professional experience. It is extremely important for teachers that students have a broad outlook, are able to express their own opinions, and respond thoughtfully to social phenomena occurring in society. Critical thinking develops these abilities and undoubtedly helps a child to succeed in any field of science in the future.

Critical thinking is one of the teaching technologies that has received significant attention and effective implementation in our country today. The 21st century is an era of educated individuals, marked by rapid development of information and modern technologies, and continuous growth of scientific and cultural innovations. In order not to lag behind this progress and to ensure that our country has high prestige on the world stage, clear goals, and a bright future, special attention must be paid to students' literacy and language proficiency.

During the course, we sought to master a variety of teaching methods and forms to enhance students' interest. Among the components of the course—dialogic teaching, formative assessment, critical thinking, and teaching and learning through the use of ICT—the one that impressed me the most was critical thinking.

From an early age, every child should be encouraged to think freely, achieve their goals, overcome obstacles, and adapt to challenges. Therefore, forming students' critical perspectives on various issues in each lesson and encouraging them to speak openly and freely is the responsibility of every teacher. Critical thinking is a method used to understand, evaluate, analyze, and synthesize information obtained through observation, experience, reflection, and reasoning, and it can also serve as a basis and motivation for action.

Critical thinking often involves the ability to imagine possibilities, make alternative decisions, and be prepared to introduce new or modified ways of thinking and acting. It also implies a willingness to engage in organized social activities and to encourage others to think critically. At the initial level, the critical thinking process includes:

- collecting relevant information;
- critically analyzing and evaluating evidence;
- making well-founded decisions and drawing synthesized conclusions;
- revisiting assumptions and recommendations based on extensive experience.

Along with complex tasks such as critical thinking in teaching and learning, this process includes recognizing implicit assumptions and values, identifying problems, finding effective tools to solve them, and understanding the importance of setting priorities when addressing various tasks. In critical thinking, a child first synthesizes the necessary information mentally, then provides examples to support their opinion, evaluates the correctness or incorrectness of this viewpoint from their own perspective, presents the accumulated conclusions for discussion, and, if opposing views arise, attempts to give reasoned responses while maintaining their position.

All of these processes take place within a matter of seconds. If ten to twelve minutes of a lesson are devoted to critical thinking, each student receives only one or two minutes. Within that limited time, organizing, synthesizing, developing, and articulating thoughts clearly helps to cultivate students' skills and mastery. Through actions (gestures), as well as non-verbal and verbal means, students attempt to convince their classmates of the validity of their ideas. This enables them in the future to express their opinions clearly and convincingly about any social phenomenon or global event.

Only when a child experiences freedom of thought and freedom of expression can they discover scientific and technological innovations. Critical thinking is usually associated with later stages of education—upper secondary school and higher

education. However, the foundations of critical thinking can be developed from the early stages of education while working with young children, with the aim of fostering essential skills. The most effective approach in this process is encouraging children to pay attention to evidence drawn from their own experiences.

We have ample examples from everyday life in different parts of the world and across various historical periods that can be used to spark children's interest and develop their critical thinking skills. Critical thinking involves developing skills such as gathering evidence through observation and listening, taking context into account, and applying appropriate criteria to make well-reasoned decisions.

The ability to express one's thoughts concisely, to avoid hesitation when presenting an opinion, and to adapt to clarity within a set time limit naturally draws attention to the weight and balance of one's argument. During the lesson, students think comprehensively and recall knowledge gained from other subjects, making every effort to present their ideas in an expressive and well-supported manner. Critical thinking not only enables students to articulate their opinions consciously, but also trains them to ask thoughtful and literate questions.

When any student attempts to challenge an opponent, the most effective way to do so is by asking an appropriate question. By asking questions, the student posing the question seeks the answer, while the student responding draws upon all their knowledge to provide a precise reply. This form of intellectual competition sparks the interest of the remaining students and creates an atmosphere of critical thinking throughout the classroom. The teacher, too, should not remain neutral, but is obliged to express various viewpoints together with the students and stimulate reflection on them.

Let us consider how these stages are implemented. First, students become familiar with the new lesson material (visual aids, handouts, texts, and video materials related to the lesson). The second stage is comprehension. At this stage, becoming acquainted with aphorisms, scientific hypotheses, and new findings related to the topic plays a significant role, because for an opinion to be formed, the student must thoroughly understand the topic. During the comparison stage, students compare their accumulated ideas and knowledge with the viewpoints of scholars and with their own perspectives. The next stage is synthesis, during which students carefully analyze and organize their thoughts, gradually arriving at a clear and definite opinion.

The stages of evaluation and application form the final phase. At this point, issues such as how classmates evaluate the opinion and whether it has the potential to be applied in practice are considered. Studies aimed at examining classroom interaction have shown that certain patterns of interaction—such as exploratory talk, evidence-based reasoning, and dialogue—not only engage teachers and students in collaborative

meaning-making and knowledge acquisition, but also foster higher-order thinking skills and contribute to the development of intellectual abilities.

Direct interaction with visual and oral sources of information allows children to develop reasoning skills and to learn through individual approaches, while reducing formalized learning. Students often express dissatisfaction with traditional methods such as learning solely through textbooks; therefore, teachers need to reconsider their roles—not as controllers of knowledge and inquiry processes, but as guides who support and direct them. Thus, dialogue plays a crucial role in nurturing critical thinking in children.

Not only reading a text, but also being able to formulate questions related to it and receive answers from classmates has a significant impact on the development of critical thinking. In this regard, the teacher's active involvement is also essential. Asking questions beyond the textbook related to a topic or a new development, and allowing students to provide a variety of responses—regardless of whether they are correct or incorrect—is important, as it encourages students to freely express their thoughts.

Dialogic teaching and critical thinking develop in very close interrelation with one another. Through dialogue, critical thinking enhances students' mechanical memory skills (such as rules repeatedly practiced in daily lessons, analyses, declension and conjugation, and questions related to lexical topics). By engaging students in various games (such as "Auction," "Field of Wonders," "Crosswords," and others), previously covered material is recalled. In the concluding part of the lesson, discussion through dialogue between the teacher and students helps reduce errors and risks, narrow choices, and accelerate the transmission of concepts and principles. Structured, cumulative talk and discussion foster mutual understanding and promote collaborative meaning-making.

The teacher must clearly establish agreements regarding the rules of dialogue and create a model of dialogic interaction in the classroom. Students, in turn, should work by searching for new and most effective approaches and by engaging in collaborative ways of constructing meaning. To achieve this, it is necessary to understand students' individual characteristics and interests, and to pay attention to their interactions and emotions. By listening to and analyzing what students do and say, and by responding appropriately, teachers gain opportunities to provide effective support for students' learning. The concept of "assessment as learning" and the principle of formative assessment imply learning not only by acquiring knowledge, but also by participating in methods that help construct that knowledge. Dialogic teaching combined with critical thinking plays an important role in students' lives. In this context, Alexander's theory of *Dialogic Teaching* serves as a foundation. According

to this theory, an examination of applied classroom research casts doubt on classroom interaction models in which students' opinions are overlooked or only minimally considered from the perspective of dialectical and dialogic pedagogy. Direct interaction with visual and oral sources of information helps children express their thoughts in a reasoned and coherent manner. In line with Kazakhstan's new professional development program, teachers who think critically may rely on the structures and processes related to critical thinking described above. However, first and foremost, it is necessary to analyze the concept of reflective teaching and to take into account the need for critical thinking within the educational curriculum.

Critical thinking is presented as a purposeful, self-regulating thinking process that is based on the ability to use evidence and context, conclusions and methods, as well as criteria. In developing children's critical thinking abilities—particularly skills such as learning through listening and inquiry, paying attention to context, and applying appropriate criteria for decision-making—teachers must also develop the theoretical foundations, methods, and technologies necessary to understand the curriculum and the teaching and learning process, as well as to form sound conclusions and judgments.

The critical thinking teaching program consists of various strategies.

I currently use fifteen of them in my lessons. These include:

1. Visualizing the main idea
2. Clustering
3. Essay writing
4. Edward de Bono's Six Thinking Hats
5. Bloom's Taxonomy
6. Gallery walk
7. Venn diagram
8. Author's chair
9. Bus stop
10. Yes–No
11. Brainstorming
12. Thick and thin questions
13. Cinquain
14. Fishbone
15. Brain activation (stimulating thinking)

I am convinced that significant success can be achieved through the use of the strategies listed above. For making daily lessons engaging—and most importantly, for ensuring a high level of student participation—these strategies are invaluable. There are also other strategies such as “*Black Box*,” “*PIM*,” “*IDEAL*,” “*Cluster*,”

“*INSERT*,” and others. I have not yet implemented these methods in my own practice, but in the future I plan to apply them as well, making every effort to ensure that my lessons are conducted at a high level.

Through the “*Brain Activation*” strategy, students have learned to write about what impressed them, the ideas they gained, and the thoughts they formed from the studied topic. In the initial lessons, students were limited to retelling the content, but in later lessons they began to focus on revealing the author’s ideas as well.

The “*Edward de Bono’s Six Thinking Hats*” strategy is particularly effective in teaching the Kazakh language, especially for lower-grade students. First, children are eager to wear the hats (it is important that they are colorful), which creates a positive atmosphere in the classroom. Once they put on the hats, their sense of responsibility increases. This strategy strongly encourages students to demonstrate their knowledge and strive for leadership. Second, it helps students view a single topic from multiple perspectives.

For example, what six different aspects can be explored about a fox? How might students respond?

- **White hat:** where it lives;
- **Black hat:** what color its fur is;
- **Red hat:** what it feeds on;
- **Green hat:** whether it exists in Kazakhstan;
- **Pink hat:** whether it lives in a zoo or not;

Thus, by examining a single fox from multiple perspectives, we see that it is possible to gain extensive information about it.

Through the use of **Venn diagrams**, students compare characters and animals. This strategy enables them to gain a deeper understanding of traits and to explore values such as humanity, honesty, and integrity.

The **clustering strategy** enables students to think freely, explore a topic openly, and integrate new ideas. This strategy can be implemented in group work, pair work, or individual activities. By dividing students into groups, the following outcomes can be achieved:

1. Reaching a shared conclusion, meaning that members of a group align their thinking on a particular issue;
2. Developing common interests and strengthening unity and cooperation;
3. Engaging all students in the learning process, as leadership roles rotate frequently and even students who are less confident in responding become active participants;
4. Identifying and clearly defining unclear aspects of the topic through open discussion.

Students who work in this manner achieve more effective learning outcomes. Reflective teaching involves students thinking critically about what they have learned. This requires examining, recording, and evaluating the critical thinking skills they demonstrate. These abilities and skills become evident when students complete tasks that require discussing and analyzing specific evidence within the learning process.

Through such tasks, students may learn, for example, about travelers and transportation, as these topics explore people's life journeys and help identify human needs, or they may learn about historical changes and continuous inquiry, gaining insight into the relationships between the environment and technology that influence social and economic life. In general, students who think critically are active in any environment and across all subjects. They ask meaningful questions, express well-supported opinions, and make connections with other disciplines in order to construct meaning.

In contrast, students who think narrowly and remain confined to one-sided perspectives are unlikely to make scientific discoveries in the future. In schools where Kazakh is taught to students of other nationalities, expressing one's thoughts fluently in Kazakh can present difficulties. However, if students consistently participate actively in lessons and make every effort to master the strategies mentioned above, this challenge can undoubtedly be overcome.

Although the process may initially be difficult due to limited vocabulary, incorrect use of grammatical forms (suffixes and endings), and a lack of oral practice, I can confidently state that through continuous speaking practice—even if students do not become eloquent speakers—they will still develop the ability to express their ideas clearly and effectively at an appropriate level.

According to the “**Critical Thinking**” instructional technology, a modular lesson consists of three stages: [1, p. 67]

1. **Engagement (arousing interest)**
2. **Implementation (constructing meaning: comprehension and understanding)**
3. **Reflection (thoughtful consideration)** — focusing attention on one's own consciousness and psychological state

Engagement

- Activating the learner's prior knowledge and experience;
- Encouraging active participation by students;
- Forming motivation (rationale) for learning activities;
- Setting individual learning goals for students within the learning process.
- Acquiring new knowledge with the learner;

- Understanding the relationship between prior knowledge and new information, forming comprehension, and systematizing knowledge;
- Learning work methods using information;
- Supporting the objectives set during the engagement stage.

Implementation

INSERT is an effective tool that teaches students to comprehend what they read, guide their own thinking, and express their ideas. Using this method, students are assigned to read a text or study a topic while marking it with the following symbols:

- V – “I know this”
- – – “This is unclear to me”
- + – “This is new information for me”
- ? – “This surprises me”

In English lessons, new methods can be demonstrated using an interactive board. Additionally, during presentations, a variety of teaching techniques can be applied to explain the lesson.

For example, I chose the topic “**Sweet Swan of Avon**” on the English playwright W. Shakespeare for an English class. In this lesson, while explaining the content and staging a scene to help students understand, the following methods can be used. [2, p. 24]

METHODS

1. **Jigsaw Reading**
2. **Picture Gallery**
3. **T-Table**
4. **Münsterberg Method**

T-Table

William	Anne
William Shakespeare, the greatest English poet and dramatist was born on the 23 rd of April, 1564 in Stratford-on-Avon in Eglad.	She was 8 years older than William. _____ _____ _____

We used this method to provide information about the two main characters. When applying this method, it can also be used to describe the positive and negative traits of characters in the work. Additionally, the **T-Table** method can be used to compare two topics or two objects. For example, as a result of using this method,

students are able to learn about the characters in the work and identify their good and bad qualities. [3, p. 29]

Picture Gallery Method

Let’s make a small trip to these places:

1. Shakespeare’s birthplace
2. Anne Hathaway’s Cottage (the early home of Shakespeare’s wife)
3. The foundations and gardens of the place where Shakespeare died
4. Hall’s Croft (the home of his daughter Susannah)
5. Mary Arden’s House (the home of the poet’s mother)

I used this method to organize a “trip” through the places in Shakespeare’s life. This method helps students gain a deeper understanding of the locations related to Shakespeare’s childhood, the periods he lived through, and his literary works. Organizing it as a “trip” also makes it interesting for students, as they move around the classroom and learn about these places or see their pictures while simulating a journey.

Jigsaw reading activity:

table 3

was	in the	in Henly	house
born	Shakespeare		
Hathaway	that	Shakespeare	married at the
was	Anne	the woman	age of 18

In this method, students are required to rearrange sentences related to the topic into the correct order. This helps develop the student’s thinking skills and also teaches them how to use interactive boards effectively. While completing the given task, students think deeply and try to find solutions more quickly, which ultimately broadens their intellectual horizon.

Munsterberg Method

Among many letters, there are complete words. The student’s task is to read quickly and underline these words.

Example:

hagkgkjbbkskbooksfalanguageslg;criticensdkthinkingklgmethodsafleffectivesgevalu
 ate.

Task: How many words can you find?

- What do I already know?
- What new information did I learn?
- How has my knowledge changed?
- What can I do with this knowledge?

By using the above methods:

1. Jigsaw Reading
2. Five-Line Poem
3. T-Table
4. Münsterberg Method

students can achieve the following:

- Improve their knowledge
- Solve problem-based tasks
- Discuss the assigned task (express ideas, share with peers, present to the group), which expands their thinking skills
- Enrich their vocabulary by learning new words
- Integrate new information with their prior knowledge
- Acquire new knowledge and connect it meaningfully with what they already know

To teach **critical thinking**, attention should be paid to the following requirements:

- Teaching critical thinking requires time;
- Allow students to express their ideas openly without immediately judging them as right or wrong;
- Present and discuss diverse ideas and opinions (from the teacher's side);
- Require students to speak with reasoning and organize their thoughts clearly;
- Most importantly, evaluate their opinions.

By using critical thinking, students:

1. Increase their curiosity;
2. Develop their individual abilities;
3. Learn to express their opinions;
4. Pay attention to clarity and accuracy.

In conclusion, we live in the era of knowledge. As our President said, "*In the modern world, the strength of a nation is primarily measured by the knowledge of its citizens.*" To become a competitive country and thrive in the global arena, it is crucial that children are knowledgeable, well-mannered, and able to think deeply. To make innovations in any field of science and contribute to the future development of our country, our thinking must be free and our language eloquent.

CONCLUSION

Critical thinking is the ability of an individual to analyze, research, and summarize issues in any situation and freely express their thoughts. It is a form of independent thinking. It involves:

- Asking questions and continuously seeking answers;

- Identifying problems that require solutions;
- Expressing opinions on various issues and providing evidence to support them;
- Carefully considering the opinions of others and analyzing the logic of supporting evidence.

In summary, a person who can think critically in the process of learning English gains the following opportunities:

- Develops students' communicative competence and can solve problem-based tasks;
- Enhances the ability to think critically in English;
- Improves language skills and creative abilities in oral and written communication;
- Actively, intelligently, and competitively integrates prior knowledge with new information, thereby advancing their overall knowledge.

Each method of critical thinking has its peculiarities. Therefore, in the course of the research work, each technique contributed to the development of students' different skills. The methods used had a positive effect on the students of group A, taken as an experimental group. Since the primary goal of the research is to develop the skills of public speaking students through critical thinking methods, the chosen methods are considered the most effective. In addition, when using methods in the course of the lesson, it is necessary to make them relevant to the topic Conclusion. Developing students' public speaking skills is one of the most necessary skills today, especially important for students. In this regard, the use of critical thinking methods in the education system contributes to developing students' public speaking skills This study examined how students develop public speaking skills. In developing these skills in students, critical thinking techniques were considered the most effective. It was considered an important and valuable way to improve students ' public speaking in the study.

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